

STUDENTS' SATISFACTION TOWARDS ONLINE LEARNING AND THEIR ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN MATHEMATICS

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this study was to determine the relationship and difference of the students' satisfaction towards online learning in Mathematics as to their profile. A descriptive correlation design was utilized in the study. This study employed inferential statistics to test the hypotheses. This study focused on the students' level of satisfaction and academic performance in Mathematics of 121 Junior High School students at Jet Montessori School of Ramon, Inc. The results of the study revealed that the students were confident that they are satisfied with online mathematics learning. The study showed that there was no significant difference in their level of satisfaction when grouped according to their profile, specifically age, gender, gadgets, internet connection, internet usages and to their academic performance. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant relationship between their level of satisfaction and the use of TV/Radio, and had an insignificant relationship between the level of satisfaction and the use of gadget. On the other hand, it showed no significant relationship between their level of satisfaction and the use of internet connection in learning. Moreover, it showed no significant relationship between level of satisfaction and the used of internet per week in learning. Lastly, the relationship between the respondents' level of satisfaction on online learning in mathematics and their academic performance showed no significant relationship. Majority of the respondents were 15 years old. Most of them were female. With regards to the gadgets used, majority of the respondents had an android phone. On their internet connection, most of them were using PLDT Home Fiber and in the frequency

of use, majority of them used the internet every day. For the relationship between the respondents' level of satisfaction in learning mathematics, there was no significant relationship between their level of satisfaction and their age, gender, internet connection, gadgets and internet usage. On the relationship between the respondents' level of satisfaction in learning mathematics and academic performance, the results revealed that there was no significant relationship between the level of satisfaction and their academic performance.

Keywords: *Satisfaction, Academic Performance, Mathematics, Online Learning*

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic, caused by the novel coronavirus, has significantly impacted various sectors globally, particularly the education system. In response to safety protocols and measures implemented by the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF), such as staying at home, wearing masks, and maintaining physical distancing, traditional classroom-based learning was disrupted (World Health Organization [WHO], 2020). Consequently, online learning emerged as the primary alternative for continuing education, especially during prolonged lockdowns.

The Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines adopted online learning as a solution to ensure that education persisted despite the pandemic's challenges. The researchers of this study recognize that online learning, while innovative, introduced complexities in delivering an effective and efficient teaching-learning process, particularly in mathematics. Numerous studies underscore the importance of fostering student satisfaction in online education, as it significantly correlates with academic performance and learning outcomes (Kuo et al., 2013).

Satisfaction in online learning is multidimensional and influenced by factors such as communication, participation, flexibility, and instructor characteristics (Keengwe, et al., 2012). However, the sudden shift to the "new normal" highlighted the lack of preparedness among educators and institutions to effectively transition to online learning platforms (Mahmood et al., 2012). Despite these challenges, online education has allowed students to continue pursuing their dreams and develop skills necessary for their future academic and professional endeavors.

The researchers conducted this study to address the gaps in understanding student satisfaction in online mathematics learning, particularly among junior high school students at Jet Montessori School of Ramon, Inc. The study titled "**Students' Satisfaction towards Online Learning and their Academic Performance in Mathematics**" seeks to examine the relationship between students' satisfaction levels and their academic performance. Furthermore, it aims to identify the factors influencing satisfaction and their implications for improving online education.

This research is timely and relevant as it provides insights into optimizing online learning environments, especially in mathematics, where traditional teaching methods are

often deemed indispensable. The findings will benefit students, educators, institutions, and parents by enhancing the strategies and tools used in online education, thereby ensuring that learning remains engaging, effective, and aligned with academic standards.

Research Questions

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender;
 - 1.3 Technology used in learning on-line in terms of:
 - 1.3.1 Gadgets;
 - 1.3.2 internet connection; and
 - 1.3.3 internet usage?
 - 1.4 General Weighted Average;
2. What is the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics as perceived by the respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1 Effectiveness of the feedback;
 - 2.2 Timeliness of the feedback;
 - 2.3 Use of discussion boards;
 - 2.4 Dialogue between instructors and students;
 - 2.5 Perceptions of online experiences;
 - 2.6 Instructor characteristics;
 - 2.7 The feel of a learning community; and
 - 2.8 Computer-mediated communication?
3. What is the difference in the level of satisfaction on online learning in mathematics when grouped according to their profile?
4. What is the relationship in the level of satisfaction on online learning in mathematics when grouped according to their profile?

METHODOLOGY

1. The study was conducted at a private educational institution in Isabela during the Academic Year 2021–2022, focusing on junior high school students' satisfaction with online learning and their academic performance in mathematics. A descriptive-correlational design was employed to explore relationships among variables, including demographics, technology use, satisfaction levels, and academic outcomes.

2. The respondents included 121 students from Grades 7 to 10, proportionally distributed across grade levels to ensure balanced representation. Data were gathered using a structured questionnaire, which had two main parts: respondent profile and satisfaction

level. The satisfaction component utilized a validated Likert-scale instrument adapted from Davis (2017).

3. Statistical analysis, conducted using SPSS software, included frequency, percentage, mean, and Kendall's Tau-B to describe and analyze relationships between variables. The study's findings were limited to the sampled students, the academic year, and the subject of mathematics, with no generalizations made to other contexts or disciplines.

RESULTS

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 shows the respondents' age, gender, gadgets used, internet connection, frequency of internet use and academic performance in Mathematics.

Age. As seen from the table, majority of the respondents were 15 years old with a total of 39 or 32.20 percent, 14 years old with a total of 32 or 26.40 percent, 13 years old with a total of 39 or 24 percent, 12 years old with a total of 13 or 10.70 percent and the least is 16 years old with a total of 8 or 6.60 percent.

Gender. Most of the respondents were female with a total of 63 or 52.10 percent, the males have a total of 52 or 43 percent and LGBTQ+ was the least with 6 or 5 percent.

Gadgets Used. On the gadgets used, most of the respondents used android phones with a total of 94 or 77.70 percent, laptop was used by 37 or 30.60 percent, the desktop was used by 12 or 9.90 percent, the tablet was by 8 or 6.60 percent and the least was TV/Radio with 2 or 1.70 percent.

Internet Connection. For internet connection, majority of the respondents used PLDT Home Fiber with 80 or 66.10 percent, 30 or 22.80 percent used mobile data, 22 or 18.20 percent used Globe Broadband, and the least number used the smart broadband with 2 or 1.70 percent.

Frequency of Internet Use. For the frequency of internet use, majority of the respondents used internet every day with a total of 86 or 71.10 percent, 16 or 13.20 percent for once to two times a week, 11 or 9.10 percent with five times to seven times a week and 8 or 6.60 percent for three to four times a week.

Table 1. Respondents' Age, Gender, Gadgets used, Internet Connection, Frequency usage and Academic Performance in Mathematics (n = 121).

PROFILE	Frequency	Percent
<u>Age</u>		
12 Years Old	13	10.70
13 Years Old	29	24.00
14 Years Old	32	26.40
15 Years Old	39	32.20
16 Years Old	8	6.60
<u>Gender</u>		
Male	52	43.00
Female	63	52.10
LGBTQ+	6	5.00
<u>Gadgets Used</u>		
Android	94	77.70
Desktop	12	9.90
Laptop	37	30.60
Tablet	8	6.60
TV/Radio	2	1.70
<u>Internet Connection</u>		
Mobile Data	30	2.80
Globe Broadband	22	18.20
PLDT Home Fiber	80	66.10
Smart Broadband	2	1.70
<u>Frequency of Internet Use</u>		
Once to two times week	16	13.20
Three to four times a week	8	6.60
Five times to Seven times	11	9.10
Everyday	86	71.10
<u>Academic Performance in Mathematics</u>		
75-79 (Fairly Satisfactory)	1	0.80
80-84 (Satisfactory)	11	9.10
85-89 (Very Satisfactory)	64	52.90
90-100 (Excellent)	45	37.20
<i>Mean = 88.00 (Very Satisfactory)</i>		

Academic Performance in Mathematics. For the academic performance in mathematics, majority of the respondents had a grade range of 85-89 or very satisfactory with 64 or 52.90 percent, 45 or 37.20 percent with a grade range from 90 to 100 which indicated excellent, 11 or 9.10 percent with a grade range of 80 to 84 which indicated satisfactory and the least with a grade range of 75 to 79 which indicated fairly satisfactory with 1 or 0.80 percent.

Students' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics

Table 2 shows the respondent's level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of effectiveness of feedback, timeliness of feedback and use of discussion boards.

Effectiveness of Feedback. As reflected on the table, the respondents rated agree for "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of clarification for my questions about the course (e.g. assignments), "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of instruction on how to fix incorrect problems in assignments, and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of sufficient explanations on my specific questions related to my class work" with a mean rating of 4.01, 4.03 and 3.98 respectively which implied that they agreed with effectiveness of feedback in terms of online learning in Mathematics.

Timeliness of Feedback. As seen on the table, the respondents appraised agree for "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to complete my assignments efficiently", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to improve my assignments for better grades" and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am more focused on learning" with a mean rating of 3.99, 3.99 and 3.97 respectively which implied that they agreed with the timeliness of feedback in terms of online learning in Mathematics.

Use of Discussion Boards. It is shown in the table that respondents rated agree for "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because discussion boards make me more comfortable in participating than traditional modes of discussion", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because asynchronous discussions (where I can post my discussions at any time of the day) are more convenient to my schedule than traditional discussions" and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I have plenty of time to think and draft my responses for online discussions" with a mean rating of 3.94, 3.96, and 4.03 respectively which implied that they agreed with the use of discussion boards in terms of online learning in Mathematics.

Table 2. Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of Effectiveness of Feedback, Timeliness of the Feedback and Use of Discussion Boards.

STATEMENTS	Mean	Description
Effectiveness of Feedback		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of clarification for my questions about the course (e.g. assignments).	4.01	Agree
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of instruction on how to fix incorrect problems in assignments.	4.03	Agree
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of sufficient explanations on my specific questions related to my class work.	3.98	Agree
Timeliness of the Feedback		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to complete my assignments efficiently.	3.99	Agree
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to improve my assignments for better grades.	3.99	Agree
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am more focused on learning.	3.97	Agree
Use of Discussion Boards		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because discussion boards make me more comfortable in participating than traditional modes of discussion.	3.94	Agree
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because asynchronous discussions (where I can post my discussions at any time of the day) are more convenient to my schedule than traditional discussions.	3.96	Agree
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I have plenty of time to think and draft my responses for online discussions.	4.02	Agree

Table 3 shows the respondent's level of satisfaction of online learning in Mathematics in terms of dialogue between instructors and students, perceptions in online experiences, instructor characteristics, the feel of a learning community, and computer-mediated communication.

Dialogue between instructors and students. The table shows that the respondents rated agree for "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I am able to communicate effectively with my instructor throughout the semester", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online dialogue with my instructor helps me as I learn in the online course", with a mean rating of 4.02, 3.96, and 3.93 respectively which implied that they agreed with the dialogue between instructors and students in terms of online learning in Mathematics.

Perceptions of Online Experiences. It was reflected on the table that the respondents' rated agree for all the indicators of perceptions of online experiences with a mean rating of 3.94, 3.98 and 3.93 respectively. This implied that they agreed with perceptions of online experiences in terms of online learning in Mathematics. As to the instructor characteristics, in the table it is shown that the respondents rated agree for all the statements of instructor characteristics with a mean rating of 4.02, 3.98, and 4.00 respectively. This implied that they agreed with instructor characteristics in terms of online learning in mathematics. As to the feel of a learning community, the table shows that the respondents agreed for all the indicators of the feel of a learning community with a mean rating of 4.02, 3.93 and 3.99 respectively which implied that they agreed with the feel of a learning community in terms of online learning in mathematics.

Computer-mediated Communication. The table reflects that the respondents' rated agreed for "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes me feel like a real person when I communicate in the online environment", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes it easier to form meaningful relationships among students in the online environment", and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication allows me to feel the presence of my instructor and other students in the online environment" with a mean rating of 3.87, 3.92 and 3.87 respectively which implied that they agreed with computer-mediated as to online learning in mathematics.

Table 3. Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of Dialogue between Instructors and Students, Perceptions of On-line Experiences, Instructor Characteristics, the Feel of a Learning Community and Computer-Mediated Communication.

STATEMENTS	Mean	Description
Dialogue between Instructors and Students		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I am able to communicate effectively with my instructor throughout the semester.	4.02	Agree
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online dialogue with my instructor helps me as I learn in the online course.	3.96	Agree
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I feel less distant in my online learning due to online dialogue with my instructor.	3.93	Agree
Perceptions of Online Experiences		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because my personal needs as a student are met in the online environment.	3.94	Agree
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because many aspects (features) of online education are enjoyable to me as a learner.	3.98	Agree
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because overall, I would rather take online courses than traditional courses.	3.93	Agree
Instructor Characteristics		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I still get the same explanation from online instructors as I do from traditional instructors.	4.02	Agree
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online instructors and traditional instructors offer the same amount of help with my learning issues.	3.98	Agree
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because technology makes online instructors more creative in teaching than a more traditional classroom.	4.00	Agree
The feel of a Learning Community		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is like a community where I can communicate with other students.	4.02	Agree
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment promotes sufficient sharing and caring among students.	3.93	Agree
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is a safe place where I can be confident in completing group work with other students in the class.	3.99	Agree
Computer-Mediated communication		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes me feel like a real person when I communicate in the online environment.	3.87	Agree
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes it easier to form meaningful relationships among students in the online environment.	3.92	Agree

3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication allows me to feel the presence of my instructor and other students in the online environment.	3.87	Agree
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Difference in Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics according to Gender

Table 4 shows the difference in the respondent's level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of effectiveness of feedback, timeliness of the feedback and use of discussion boards according to gender.

Effectiveness of Feedback. As indicated on the table, the respondents agreed that they were satisfied with online learning in terms of clarification for their questions about the course (e.g. assignments), instruction on how to fix incorrect problems in their assignments, and sufficient explanations on their specific questions related to their class work with mean ratings of 3.94, 4.08, and 3.94 for male, mean ratings of 4.06, 4.00, and 4.10 for the female and mean ratings of 4.00, 4.00 and 4.17 for LGBTQ+.

The Chi-square values from 0.44 to 1.02 and significance level greater than 0.05 shows insignificant differences of the level satisfaction of online learning in mathematics according to gender. This led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which implied that male, female and LGBTQ+ had the same perceptions in terms of the effectiveness of feedback in their online learning in terms of clarification for their questions about the course (e.g. assignments), instruction on how to fix incorrect problems in assignments, and sufficient explanations on their specific questions related to their class work.

Timeliness of Feedback. As seen on the table, the mean rating from 4.33 to 3.87 indicated that male, female, and LGBTQ+ respondents agreed that they were satisfied with the timeliness of feedback in their online learning experience because timely feedback related to their class work constantly provided them ability to complete their assignments efficiently, improve their assignments for better grades, and become more focused on learning with the Chi-square values from 2.13 to 3.66 and significance level greater than 0.05. This led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. It shows insignificant difference between the timeliness of feedback and the gender of the respondents and implies that male, female and LGBTQ+ had the same perceptions in terms of the timeliness of feedback in their online learning for timely feedback related to their class work constantly provided them ability to complete their assignments efficiently.

Use of Discussion Boards. It was shown from the table that the male, female and LGBTQ+ agree that they were satisfied with the use of discussion boards in their online learning experience because discussion boards make them more comfortable in participating than traditional modes of discussion., asynchronous discussions (where I can post my discussions at any time of the day) were more convenient to their schedule

than traditional discussions, and they have plenty of time to think and draft their responses for online discussions with mean ratings of 3.90 to 4.17.

The Chi-square values from 0.33 to 0.78 and significance level greater than 0.05 shows insignificant relationship between the use of discussion boards and the gender of the respondents which led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implies that male, female and LGBTQ+ had the same perceptions in terms of the use of discussion boards.

Table 4. Difference in Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of Effectiveness of Feedback, Timeliness of the Feedback and Use of Discussion Boards according to Gender.

STATEMENTS	Male		Female		LGBTQ+		Chi- Square	Sig.
	Mean	Desc.	Mean	Desc.	Mean	Desc.		
<u>Effectiveness of Feedback</u>								
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of clarification for my questions about the course (e.g. assignments).	3.94	Agree	4.06	Agree	4.00	Agree	1.02 ^{ns}	0.60
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of instruction on how to fix incorrect problems in assignments.	4.08	Agree	4.00	Agree	4.00	Agree	0.44 ^{ns}	0.80
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of sufficient explanations on my specific questions related to my class work.	3.94	Agree	4.00	Agree	4.17	Agree	0.81 ^{ns}	0.67
<u>Timeliness of the Feedback</u>								
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to complete my assignments efficiently.	3.90	Agree	4.06	Agree	4.00	Agree	2.13 ^{ns}	0.35
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to improve my assignments for better grades.	3.87	Agree	4.08	Agree	4.17	Agree	3.66 ^{ns}	0.16
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am more focused on learning.	3.88	Agree	4.00	Agree	4.33	Agree	3.05 ^{ns}	0.22
<u>Use of Discussion Boards</u>								
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because discussion boards make me more comfortable in participating than traditional modes of discussion.	3.94	Agree	3.92	Agree	4.17	Agree	0.71 ^{ns}	0.70
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because asynchronous discussions (where I can post my discussions at any time of the day) are more convenient to my schedule than traditional discussions.	4.02	Agree	3.90	Agree	4.00	Agree	0.78 ^{ns}	0.68
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I have plenty of time to think and draft my responses for online discussions.	4.02	Agree	4.00	Agree	4.17	Agree	0.33 ^{ns}	0.85

Table 5 shows the difference in respondents' level of satisfaction of online learning in Mathematics in terms of dialogue between instructors and students, perceptions of online experiences and instructor characteristics according to gender.

Dialogue between instructors and students. As seen from the table, the male, female and LGBTQ+ respondents agree that they were satisfied in their online learning experience because they are able to communicate effectively with their instructor throughout the semester, instructor helps them as they learn in the online course, and they feel less distant in their online learning due to online dialogue with their instructor with mean ratings from 3.83 to 4.05. The Chi-square values from 0.08 to 0.54 and significance level greater than 0.05 led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implies that male, female and LGBTQ+ had the same perceptions in terms of the dialogue between instructors for they were able to communicate effectively with their instructor throughout the semester, instructor helps them as they learn in the online course, and they feel less distant in their online learning due to online dialogue with their instructor.

Perceptions in Online Experiences. As shown in the table, the mean ratings from 3.83 to 4.02 shows that the male, female and LGBTQ+ agree that they were satisfied in online learning mathematics in terms of personal needs as students were met in the online environment, many aspects (features) of online education were enjoyable to them as a learner, and they would rather take online courses than traditional courses. The Chi-square values from 0.09 to 0.51 and significance level greater than 0.05 shows insignificant difference and led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which implies that male, female and LGBTQ+ had the same perceptions in terms of their online learning as to the personal needs as a student were met in the online environment, many aspects (features) of online education were enjoyable to them as a learner, and they would rather take online courses than traditional courses.

Instructor Characteristics. As seen in the table it was shown that male, female and LGBTQ+ respondents agree that they were satisfied in online learning mathematics for they still get the same explanation from online instructors, online instructors and traditional instructors offer the same amount of help with their learning issues, and technology makes online instructors more creative in teaching than a more traditional classroom with mean ratings from 0.51 to 1.47. As reflected by the Chi-square values from 0.51 to 1.47 and significance level greater than 0.05 there was insignificant difference between gender and the instructor characteristics. This led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implies that male, female and LGBTQ+ had the same perceptions in terms of instructor characteristics with their online learning for they still get the same explanation from online instructors as they do from traditional instructors, online instructors and traditional instructors offer the same amount of help with their learning issues, and technology makes online instructors more creative in teaching than a more traditional classroom.

Table 5. Difference in Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of Dialogue between Instructors and Students, Perceptions of On-line Experiences and Instructor Characteristics according to Gender.

STATEMENTS	Male		Female		LGBTQ+		Chi- Square	Sig.
	Mean	Desc.	Mean	Desc.	Mean	Desc.		
<u>Dialogue between Instructors and Students</u>								
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I am able to communicate effectively with my instructor throughout the semester.	4.02	Agree	4.05	Agree	3.83	Agree	0.54 ^{ns}	0.77
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online dialogue with my instructor helps me as I learn in the online course.	3.94	Agree	3.97	Agree	4.00	Agree	0.08 ^{ns}	0.96
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I feel less distant in my online learning due to online dialogue with my instructor.	3.92	Agree	3.94	Agree	3.83	Agree	0.12 ^{ns}	0.94
<u>Perceptions of Online Experiences</u>								
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because my personal needs as a student are met in the online environment.	3.92	Agree	3.95	Agree	4.00	Agree	0.13 ^{ns}	0.94
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because many aspects (features) of online education are enjoyable to me as a learner.	3.96	Agree	4.02	Agree	3.83	Agree	0.51 ^{ns}	0.78
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because overall, I would rather take online courses than traditional courses.	3.92	Agree	3.92	Agree	4.00	Agree	0.09 ^{ns}	0.96
<u>Instructor Characteristics</u>								
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I still get the same explanation from online instructors as I do from traditional instructors.	4.02	Agree	4.03	Agree	3.83	Agree	0.51 ^{ns}	0.77
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online instructors and traditional instructors offer the same amount of help with my learning issues.	3.98	Agree	4.00	Agree	3.67	Agree	1.47 ^{ns}	0.48
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because technology makes online instructors more creative in teaching than a more traditional classroom.	4.10	Agree	3.94	Agree	3.83	Agree	1.08 ^{ns}	0.41

^{ns}Not Significant

Table 6 presents the difference in the respondents' level of satisfaction of online learning in Mathematics in terms of the feel of a learning community and computer-mediated communication according to gender.

The Feel of a Learning Community. The table shows that the mean ratings from 3.50 to 4.06 indicated that the male, female and LGBTQ+ respondents agree that they were satisfied with the feel of a learning community in online learning mathematics for the online environment was like a community where they can communicate with other students, the online environment promotes sufficient sharing and caring among students, and the online environment was a safe place where they can be confident in completing group work with other students in the class.

The Chi-square values (0.72 to 2.99) and significance level greater than 0.05 indicate no significant difference in gender perceptions of a learning community in online mathematics. This suggests that all genders felt a sense of community, effective communication, support, and a safe space for collaboration.

Computer-mediated Communication, It was reflected on the table that the mean ratings from 3.95 to 3.33 signifies that the male, female and LGBTQ+ agree that they were satisfied with online learning in mathematics in terms of computer-mediated communication for it makes them feel like a real person when they communicate in the online environment, makes it easier to form meaningful relationships among students in the online environment, and allows them to feel the presence of their instructor and other students in the online environment.

The null hypothesis was accepted for the Chi-square values from 0.19 to 5.19 and significance level greater than 0.05 for it shows no significant difference between gender and their computer-mediated communication. This implies that the male, female and LGBTQ+ had the same perceptions in terms of computer-mediated communication for it makes them feel like a real person when they communicate in the online environment, makes it easier to form meaningful relationships among students in the online environment, and allows them to feel the presence of my instructor and other students in the online environment.

Characteristics such as age, gender, and status all influence how people communicate (Hollingshead et al. 2002). In general, interactions between peer groups tend to perpetuate gender stereotypes (Bravo Gilbert, & Kearney, 2003). In the traditional classroom, female students interact and participate more than male students (Howard & Henney, 2008).

This discontinuity between the genders carries over into the online learning environment, as there is evidence that men and women interact differently when using technology (Arbaugh,2010). Other research has confirmed these findings that there are differences in how men and women communicate and interact online).

Table 6. Difference in Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of the Feel of a Learning Community and Computer-Mediated Communication according to Gender.

STATEMENTS	Male		Female		LGBTQ+		Chi- Square	Sig.
	Mean	Desc.	Mean	Desc.	Mean	Desc.		
<u>The Feel of a Learning Community</u>								
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is like a community where I can communicate with other students.	4.06	Agree	4.02	Agree	3.83	Agree	0.72 ^{ns}	0.69
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment promotes sufficient sharing and caring among students.	3.92	Agree	3.97	Agree	3.50	Agree	2.99 ^{ns}	0.23
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is a safe place where I can be confident in completing group work with other students in the class.	3.98	Agree	4.03	Agree	3.67	Agree	1.67 ^{ns}	0.43
<u>Computer-Mediated Communication</u>								
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes me feel like a real person when I communicate in the online environment.	3.83	Agree	3.95	Agree	3.33	Agree	5.19 ^{ns}	0.08
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes it easier to form meaningful relationships among students in the online environment.	3.49	Agree	3.54	Agree	3.38	Agree	4.71 ^{ns}	0.09
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication allows me to feel the presence of my instructor and other students in the online environment.	2.52	Agree	3.83	Agree	3.51	Agree	0.19 ^{ns}	1.52

^{ns}Not Significant

Difference in Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics according to Age

Table 7 shows the difference in respondents' level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of effectiveness of feedback, and timeliness of the feedback according to age.

Effectiveness of Feedback. As seen on the table the respondents from 12 years old to 16 years old agree that they were satisfied in the effectiveness of feedback with mean ratings from 3.88 to 4.08 for their class work was constantly providing them clarification for their questions about the course (e.g. assignments), provided them instruction on how to fix incorrect problems in assignments, and give them sufficient explanations on their specific questions related to their class work. With this, the Chi-square values from 1.19 to 7.57 and significance level greater than 0.05 shows an insignificant difference between effectiveness of feedback and age. Thus, the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implies that the respondents from 12 to 16 years old had the same perceptions of effectiveness of feedback for their class work constantly providing them with clarification for their questions about the course (e.g. assignments), provided them instruction on how to fix incorrect problems in assignments, and give them sufficient explanations on their specific questions related to their class work.

Timeliness of Feedback. The table reflected that the respondents from 12 years old to 16 years old agree on the timeliness of the feedback has no significant difference on the level of satisfaction in online learning in mathematics for completing their assignments, improving their assignments for better grades and focused on learning with mean ratings from 3.81 to 4.08.

With this, the Chi-square values ranged from 1.24 to 2.16 and the significance level greater than 0.05 led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis for its shows insignificant difference. This implies that 12-year-old to 16 years old respondents had the same perceptions in terms of feedback specifically their online learning because completing their assignments, improving their assignments for better grades and focused on learning.

Based on the study of Ms. Antoinette Davis (2017) it was presented that age was found to be important to satisfaction with online mathematics courses but unimportant to performance in online mathematics courses. It takes the difference between gender differences and academic performance were not related to performance or satisfaction in learning mathematics online.

Table 7. Difference in Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of Effective Feedback, and Timeliness of the Feedback according to Age.

STATEMENTS	12 Years Old		13 Years Old		14 Years Old		15 years Old		16 Years Old		Chi-square	Sig.
	Mean	Desc.										
Effectiveness of Feedback												
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of clarification for my questions about the course (e.g. assignments).	4.23	Agree	3.83	Agree	3.88	Agree	4.15	Agree	4.13	Agree	7.57 ^{ns}	0.11
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of instruction on how to fix incorrect problems in assignments.	4.08	Agree	3.97	Agree	4.03	Agree	4.00	Agree	4.38	Agree	2.17 ^{ns}	0.61
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of sufficient explanations on my specific questions related to my class work.	4.00	Agree	3.90	Agree	3.97	Agree	4.03	Agree	4.13	Agree	1.19 ^{ns}	0.88
Timeliness of the Feedback												
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to complete my assignments efficiently.	4.08	Agree	3.97	Agree	3.97	Agree	3.95	Agree	4.25	Agree	2.16 ^{ns}	0.71
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to improve my assignments for better grades.	4.00	Agree	4.03	Agree	3.81	Agree	4.05	Agree	4.25	Agree	4.31 ^{ns}	0.37
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am more focused on learning.	4.08	Agree	3.97	Agree	3.88	Agree	4.00	Agree	4.00	Agree	1.24 ^{ns}	0.87

^{ns}Not Significant

Table 8 shows the difference in the respondents' level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of use of discussion boards, and dialogue between instructors and students according to age.

Use of Discussion Boards. As seen on the table the respondents from 12 years old to 16 years old agree that they were satisfied on the use of discussion boards with mean ratings from 3.76 to 4.15 for it made them more comfortable in participating than traditional modes of discussion, asynchronous discussions (where can post my discussions at any time of the day) are more convenient to their schedule than traditional discussions, and they have plenty of time to think and draft their responses for online discussions.

With this, the Chi-square values from 0.14 to 7.39 and the significance level greater than 0.05 shows insignificant difference. This led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis and implies that on the use of discussion boards for their online learning made them more comfortable in participating than traditional modes of discussion, asynchronous discussions (where I can post my discussions at any time of the day) were more convenient to their schedule than traditional discussions, and they have plenty of time to think and draft their responses for online discussions.

Dialogue between Instructors and Students. The table shows that there is no significant difference in the level of satisfaction regarding instructor-student dialogue in online mathematics learning across different age groups. Respondents aged 12 to 16 were satisfied with the dialogue, believing it helped them communicate effectively with instructors, supported their learning, and reduced feelings of distance. With Chi-square values ranging from 2.38 to 5.17 and a significance level greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted. This suggests that respondents aged 12 to 16 shared similar positive perceptions about the role of online dialogue in their learning experience.

On the contrary, Antoinette Davis (2016) found out that older students tend to be less satisfied with online mathematics courses than younger students. This finding may serve as a call for instructors to be more attentive to the way that they communicate information to older students in an online classroom. She suggested that for distance learning to be successful, instructors need to pay attention to three elements of transactional distance theory (dialogue, structure, and learner autonomy) to reduce the distance" experienced by students. The benefits of using online discussion boards and peer to peer learning for enhancing student learning are well known. Other than full online courses, their adoption in traditional learning environments complementing face-to-face teaching.

Table 8. Difference in Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of Use of Discussion Boards and Dialogue between Instructors and Students according to Age.

STATEMENTS	12 Years Old		13 Years Old		14 Years Old		15 years Old		16 Years Old		Chi-square	Sig.
	Mean	Desc.										
<u>Use of Discussion Boards</u>												
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because discussion boards make me more comfortable in participating than traditional modes of discussion.	4.08	Agree	3.97	Agree	3.81	Agree	3.92	Agree	4.25	Agree	3.48 ^{ns}	0.48
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because asynchronous discussions (where I can post my discussions at any time of the day) are more convenient to my schedule than traditional discussions.	4.15	Agree	3.76	Agree	3.84	Agree	4.08	Agree	4.25	Agree	7.39 ^{ns}	0.12
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I have plenty of time to think and draft my responses for online discussions.	4.08	Agree	4.00	Agree	4.00	Agree	4.03	Agree	4.00	Agree	0.14 ^{ns}	1.00
<u>Dialogue between Instructors and Students</u>												
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I am able to communicate effectively with my instructor throughout the semester	4.15	Agree	3.93	Agree	3.94	Agree	4.08	Agree	4.25	Agree	2.59 ^{ns}	0.63
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online dialogue with my instructor helps me as I learn in the online course	3.92	Agree	4.00	Agree	3.81	Agree	4.03	Agree	4.13	Agree	2.38 ^{ns}	0.67
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I feel less distant in my online learning due to online dialogue with my instructor	4.08	Agree	3.79	Agree	3.84	Agree	3.95	Agree	4.38	Agree	5.17 ^{ns}	0.27

^{ns}Not Significant

Table 9 shows the difference in the respondents' level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of perceptions of online experiences, and instructor characteristics according to age.

Perceptions of Online Experiences. The table showed that the respondents from 12 years old to 16 years old agree with mean rating from 3.79 to 4.38 that they were satisfied with online learning for their personal needs as a student are met in the online environment, many aspects (features) of online education were enjoyable to them as a learner, and they would rather take online courses than traditional courses.

The Chi-square values from 1.80 to 5.97 and significance level greater than 0.05 shows no significant difference between age and the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of perceptions of online experiences which led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implied that 12 years old to 16 years old respondents had the same perceptions in online learning for their personal needs as a student were met in the online environment, many aspects (features) of online education were enjoyable to them as a learner, and they would rather take online courses than traditional courses.

Instructor Characteristics. The table indicates that respondents aged 12 to 16 were satisfied with instructor characteristics in online learning. They agreed that explanations and support were comparable to traditional instructors and that technology made online teaching more creative. Chi-square values from 0.78 to 4.41 and a significance level above 0.05 showed no significant difference, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This suggests that students shared similar positive perceptions of their online instructors.

Hence, Garrison, Anderson & Archer, (2000) defines social, cognitive, and teaching presence as being essential to the student learning experience and, thus, student satisfaction. They determined that learning management system (LMS) features greatly impact perceptions of community according to the inquiry framework. In a related study, Mahmood and Malik (2012) argued that teaching presence plays the most critical role in how students evaluate online learning.

Students connect with their instructors and each other through modalities of almost every variety, greatly expanding avenues of communication. Norberg et al. (2011) development of a time-based blended learning model, for instance, modifies the instructor's role (Liu & Hwang, 2010) in learning environments based on students' synchronous and asynchronous learning preferences.

Table 9. Difference in Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of Perceptions of On-line Experiences and Instructor Characteristics according to Age.

STATEMENTS	12 Years Old		13 Years Old		14 Years Old		15 years Old		16 Years Old		Chi-square	Sig.
	Mean	Desc.										
Perceptions of Online Experiences												
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because my personal needs as a student are met in the online environment.	4.15	Agree	3.79	Agree	3.94	Agree	3.95	Agree	4.13	Agree	3.89 ^{ns}	0.42
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because many aspects (features) of online education are enjoyable to me as a learner.	4.15	Agree	3.93	Agree	3.81	Agree	4.03	Agree	4.38	Agree	5.97 ^{ns}	0.20
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because overall, I would rather take online courses than traditional courses.	4.08	Agree	3.86	Agree	3.88	Agree	3.92	Agree	4.13	Agree	1.80 ^{ns}	0.77
Instructor Characteristics												
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I still get the same explanation from online instructors as I do from traditional instructors.	4.15	Agree	4.00	Agree	3.97	Agree	4.03	Agree	4.00	Agree	0.78 ^{ns}	0.94
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online instructors and traditional instructors offer the same amount of help with my learning issues.	3.92	Agree	4.07	Agree	3.91	Agree	3.95	Agree	4.13	Agree	1.54 ^{ns}	0.82
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because technology makes online instructors more creative in teaching than a more traditional classroom.	4.08	Agree	3.90	Agree	4.09	Agree	3.90	Agree	4.38	Agree	4.41 ^{ns}	0.35

^{ns}Not Significant

Table 10 shows the difference in the respondents' level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of the feel of a learning community, and computer-mediated communication according to age.

The Feel of Learning Community. The table shows that the respondents from 12 years old to 16 years old agree that they were satisfied with the feeling of a learning community with mean rating from 3.92 to 4.48 for they believed that the online environment is like a community where they can communicate with other students, the online environment promotes sufficient sharing and caring among students, and they can be confident in completing group work with other students in the class. With this, the Chi-square values from 0.82 to 3.34 and significance level greater than 0.05 shows insignificant difference between their age and the feel of a learning community. This led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which implies that 12 years old to 16 years old respondents had the same perceptions with their online learning because the online environment was like a community where they can communicate with other students, the online environment promotes sufficient sharing and caring among students, and they can be confident in completing group work with other students in the class.

Computer-mediated Communication. The table reflects that the 12-year-old to 16 years old respondents agree that they were satisfied with computer-mediated communication. Specifically on the statements "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is like a community where I can communicate with other students", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment promotes sufficient sharing and caring among students", and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is a safe place where I can be confident in completing group work with other students in the class" with mean ratings from 3.72 to 4.25. The Chi-square values from 0.85 to 6.13 and significance level greater than 0.05 shows no significant difference between Computer-mediated Communication and age. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. This implies that 12 years old to 16 years old respondents had the same perceptions in terms of the computer-mediated communication for the online environment was like a community where they can communicate with other students, the online environment promotes sufficient sharing and caring among students, and the online environment was a safe place where they can be confident in completing group work with other students in the class.

According to Davis (2017), based on her studies found out that younger students are more satisfied in terms of online learning mathematics and compared to the older students, it seems that they experience lesser satisfaction that may affect their academic performance towards mathematics. This may serve as a basis of instructions so that instructors can communicate with students with their performance.

Table 10. Difference in Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of the Feel of a Learning Community and Computer-Mediated Communication according to Age.

STATEMENTS	12 Years Old		13 Years Old		14 Years Old		15 years Old		16 Years Old		Chi-square	Sig.
	Mean	Desc.										
<u>The Feel of a Learning Community</u>												
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is like a community where I can communicate with other students.	4.08	Agree	3.97	Agree	4.09	Agree	4.00	Agree	4.00	Agree	0.82 ^{ns}	0.94
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment promotes sufficient sharing and caring among students.	4.15	Agree	3.90	Agree	3.88	Agree	3.87	Agree	4.13	Agree	2.68 ^{ns}	0.61
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is a safe place where I can be confident in completing group work with other students in the class.	3.92	Agree	3.93	Agree	3.94	Agree	4.03	Agree	4.38	Agree	3.34 ^{ns}	0.50
<u>Computer-Mediated Communication</u>												
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes me feel like a real person when I communicate in the online environment.	4.08	Agree	3.83	Agree	3.78	Agree	3.87	Agree	4.00	Agree	2.45 ^{ns}	0.65
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes it easier to form meaningful relationships among students in the online environment.	4.00	Agree	3.83	Agree	3.94	Agree	3.92	Agree	4.00	Agree	0.85 ^{ns}	0.93
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication allows me to feel the presence of my instructor and other students in the online environment.	4.08	Agree	3.97	Agree	3.72	Agree	3.90	Agree	4.25	Agree	6.13 ^{ns}	0.19

^{ns}Not Significant

Relationship between the Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of the Use of Gadgets in Learning

Table 11 shows the relationship between the respondents' level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of effectiveness of feedback, and timeliness of the feedback and the use of gadgets in learning.

Effectiveness of Feedback. As seen on the table, correlation values from 0.07 to -0.01 and significance level from 0.97 to 0.26 indicates no significant relationship between the use of gadgets specifically android, tablet, laptop and desktop and online learning in mathematics pertaining to the effectiveness of feedback in mathematics. This resulted in the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implies that the gadgets used in learning have no bearing on their online learning experience because effective feedback or android, tablet, laptop and desktop used in learning had no direct relationship to the timeliness of feedback pertaining to the clarification of questions, instruction on how to fix incorrect problems in assignments and sufficient explanations on their specific questions related to their class work.

On the other hand, the correlation values from 0.19 to 0.20 and significance level less than 0.05 shows significant relationship between the use of TV/Radio in online learning mathematics., hence the rejection of the hypothesis. This implied that the frequent use of TV/Radio in learning on the higher the effectiveness of clarification on their questions, instruction on how to fix incorrect problems in assignments, and sufficient on their specific questions related to class work.

Timeliness of the Feedback. As shown in the table, correlation values from 0.05 to -0.05 and significance level from 0.97 to 0.26, respectively indicated no significant relationship between the use of android, tablet, laptop and desktop in online learning mathematics for the statements "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to complete my assignments efficiently", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to improve my assignments for better grades", and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am more focused on learning" with a correlation values from 0.33 to -0.04. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. The result implied that the android, tablet, laptop and desktop used in learning has no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of timeliness of the feedback.

On the other hand, a significant relationship was found between the use of TV/radio in online mathematics learning, with correlation values from 0.22 to 0.20 and a significance level from 0.64 to 0.36. This suggests that frequent use of TV/radio led to more timely feedback, improved assignments, better grades, and increased focus on learning.

Table 11. Relationship between Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of Effective Feedback and Timeliness of the Feedback and the Use of Gadgets in Learning.

STATEMENTS	Android		Tablet		Laptop		TV/ Radio		Desktop	
	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.
<u>Effectiveness of Feedback</u>										
1.I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of clarification for my questions about the course (e.g. assignments).	0.01 ^{ns}	0.94	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.97 ^s	0.02	0.83 ^{ns}	0.19 [*]	0.03	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.60
2.I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of instruction on how to fix incorrect problems in assignments.	-0.06 ^{ns}	0.49	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.87 ^{ns}	0.07	0.41 ^{ns}	0.19 [*]	0.03	-0.10 ^{ns}	0.26
3.I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of sufficient explanations on my specific questions related to my class work.	0.02 ^{ns}	0.89	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.62 ^s	0.02	0.85 ^{ns}	0.20 [*]	0.02	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.70
<u>Timeliness of the Feedback</u>										
1.I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to complete my assignments efficiently.	0.06 ^{ns}	0.51	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.56 ^{ns}	0.10	0.26 ^{ns}	0.22 [*]	0.01	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.64
2.I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to improve my assignments for better grades.	0.05 ^{ns}	0.55	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.60 ^s	0.01	0.92 ^{ns}	0.20 [*]	0.03	-0.08 ^{ns}	0.36
3.I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am more focused on learning.	0.33 ^{ns}	0.71	-0.09 ^{ns}	0.32 ^s	0.03	0.71 ^{ns}	0.20 [*]	0.02	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.43

*Significant ^{ns} Not Significant

Table 12 shows the relationship between respondents' level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of use of discussion boards, dialogue between instructors and students, and perceptions of on-line experiences, and the use of gadgets in learning.

Use of Discussion Boards. As seen on the table, correlation values from 0.04 to -0.01 and significance level from 0.96 to 0.33, respectively indicated no significant relationship. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the use of android, tablet, laptop and desktop in online learning mathematics for the statements "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because discussion boards make me more comfortable in participating than traditional modes of discussion", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because asynchronous discussions (where I can post my discussions at any time of the day) are more convenient to my schedule than traditional discussions", and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I have plenty of time to think and draft my responses for online discussions". This implies that the android, tablet, laptop and desktop used in learning had no bearing to the timeliness of feedback specifically on the clarification of questions, instruction on how to fix incorrect problems in assignments and sufficient explanations on their specific questions related to class work.

On the other hand, the correlation values from 0.19 to 0.20 and significance level less than 0.05 shows significant relationship, hence the rejection of the hypothesis. The result implies that the frequent use of TV/Radio in learning the higher the effectiveness of feedback specifically on the clarification on their questions, instruction on how to fix incorrect problems in assignments, and sufficient specific questions related to their class work.

Keengwe et al. (2012) argued that students' expectations influence the instructor's design of effective technology tools in online courses and are the key to understanding the satisfaction construct. The authors concluded that satisfaction was most impacted by learning convenience combined with the effectiveness of e-learning tools. Dziuban et al. (2007) found six key elements that contribute to students' satisfaction: enriched learning.

Dialogue between Instructors and Students. As seen on the table, correlation values from 0.04 to -0.01 and significance level from 0.96 to 0.33, respectively indicated insignificant relationship. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the use of android, tablet, laptop and desktop in online learning mathematics for the statements "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I am able to communicate effectively with my instructor throughout the semester", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online dialogue with my instructor helps me as I learn in the online course", and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I feel less distant in my online learning due to online dialogue with my instructor". The result implies that using android, tablet, laptop and desktop in learning has no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics.

Meanwhile, the correlation values from 0.18 to 0.19 and significance level less than 0.05 shows significant relationship, hence the rejection of the hypothesis. The result implies that the frequent use of TV/Radio as gadgets in learning the higher the satisfaction on the use of discussion boards where instructors and students make them more comfortable in participating than traditional modes of discussion, asynchronous discussions (where they can post their discussions at any time of the day) were more convenient to their schedule than traditional discussions, and complete their assignments efficiently, they were able to improve their assignments for better grades and they were more focused on learning.

Perceptions of Online Experiences. As reflected on the table, correlation values from 0.18 to 0.21 and significance level from 0.02 to 0.03, respectively indicated no significant relationship. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the use of android, tablet, laptop and desktop in online learning mathematics with the statements “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because my personal needs as a student are met in the online environment”, “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because many aspects (features) of online education are enjoyable to me as a learner”, and “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because overall, I would rather take online courses than traditional courses”. This implies that the use of android, tablet, laptop and desktop has no bearing in the satisfaction of the respondents to online learning in mathematics.

On contrary, the correlation values from 0.19 to 0.20 with significance level less than 0.05, shows significant relationship, hence the rejection of the null hypothesis. The result implied that the frequent use of TV/radio the higher the satisfaction that online experiences as to their personal needs as a student were met in the online environment, many aspects (features) of online education were enjoyable to them as a learner and they would rather take online courses than traditional courses.

Table 12. Relationship between Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of Use of Discussion Boards, Dialogue between Instructors and Students, and Perceptions of On-line Experiences, and the Use of Gadgets in Learning.

STATEMENTS	Android		Tablet		Laptop		TV/ Radio		Desktop	
	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.
<u>Use of Discussion Boards</u>										
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because discussion boards make me more comfortable in participating than traditional modes of discussion.	0.04 ^{ns}	0.67	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.43 ^s	0.00	0.96 ^{ns}	0.19 [*]	0.03	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.57
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because asynchronous discussions (where I can post my discussions at any time of the day) are more convenient to my schedule than traditional discussions.	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.72	-0.03 ^{ns}	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.75	0.91 ^{ns}	0.19 [*]	0.03	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.81
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I have plenty of time to think and draft my responses for online discussions.	0.01 ^{ns}	0.89	0.04 ^{ns}	0.65 ^{ns}	0.09	0.33 ^{ns}	0.18 [*]	0.04	-0.12 ^{ns}	0.16
<u>Dialogue between Instructors and Students</u>										
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I am able to communicate effectively with my instructor throughout the semester.	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.93	-0.10	0.24 ^s	0.03	0.76 ^{ns}	0.18 [*]	0.04	0.07 ^{ns}	0.45
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online dialogue with my instructor helps me as I learn in the online course.	0.02 ^{ns}	0.78	-0.03	0.74 ^{ns}	0.06	0.49 ^{ns}	0.18 [*]	0.04	0.02 ^{ns}	0.85
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I feel less distant in my online learning due to online dialogue with my instructor.	0.05 ^{ns}	0.56	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.86	-0.06 ^{ns}	0.51	0.18 [*]	0.04	-0.08 ^{ns}	0.38
<u>Perceptions of online experiences</u>										
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because my personal needs as a student are met in the online environment.	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.56	-0.08 ^{ns}	0.38	0.01 ^{ns}	0.94	0.21 [*]	0.02	-0.10 ^{ns}	0.26
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because many aspects (features) of online education are enjoyable to me as a learner.	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.88	0.10 ^{ns}	0.24	-0.09 ^{ns}	0.32	0.19 [*]	0.03	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.71
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because overall, I would rather take online courses than traditional courses.	0.00 ^{ns}	0.96	0.04 ^{ns}	0.68	0.00 ^{ns}	0.98	0.20 [*]	0.02	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.57

*Significant

^{ns} Not Significant

Table 13 shows the relationship between respondents' level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of instructor characteristics, the feel of a learning community and computer-mediated communication and the use of gadgets in learning.

Instructor Characteristics. As seen on the table, correlation values from 0.08 to -0.05 and significance level from 0.94 to 0.43, respectively indicated no significant relationship. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the use of android, tablet, laptop and desktop in online learning mathematics with the statements "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I still get the same explanation from online instructors as I do from traditional instructors", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online instructors and traditional instructors offer the same amount of help with my learning issues", and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because technology makes online instructors more creative in teaching than a more traditional classroom". This implies that the use of android, tablet, laptop and desktop has no bearing in the satisfaction of students in learning mathematics online in terms of instructor characteristics.

On the other hand, the correlation values from 0.08 to -0.04 with a significance level of less than 0.05 shows significant relationship. Thus, the rejection of the null hypothesis. The result implied that the frequent use of TV/radio the higher the satisfaction that they still get the same explanation from online instructors as they do from traditional instructors, online instructors and traditional instructors offer the amount of help with their learning issues, and technology makes online instructors more creative in teaching than a more traditional classroom.

The Feel of a Learning Community. As reflected on the table, correlation values from 0.11 to -0.04 and significance level from 0.91 to 0.10, respectively indicated no significant relationship. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the use of android, tablet, laptop and desktop in online learning mathematics with the statements "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is like a community where I can communicate with other students", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment promotes sufficient sharing and caring among students" and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is a safe place where I can be confident in completing group work with other students in the class". This implies that the use of android, tablet, laptop and desktop has no bearing in the satisfaction of students in learning mathematics online in terms of the feel of a learning community.

While the correlation values from 0.10 to -0.03 with significance level of less than 0.05 reflected a significant relationship which led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implied that the frequent use of TV/radio the higher the satisfaction on that online environment was like a community where they can communicate with other students, the online environment promotes sufficient sharing and caring among students and the online

environment was a safe place where they can be confident in completing group work with other students in class.

Computer-mediated Communication. The table displays that correlation values from 0.07 to -0.03 and significance level from 0.95 to 0.12, respectively indicated insignificant relationship. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the use of android, tablet, laptop and desktop in online learning mathematics with the statements “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes me feel like a real person when I communicate in the online environment”, “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes it easier to form meaningful relationships among students in the online environment” and “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication allows me to feel the presence of my instructor and other students in the online environment”. The result implied that using android, tablet, laptop and desktop in learning was not significant on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of computer mediated-communication.

On the other hand, the correlation values from 0.21 to 0.20 and significance level of less than 0.05 indicated a significant relationship, hence the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implied that the frequent use of TV/radio the higher the satisfaction on computer-mediated communication because it makes them feel like a real person when they communicate in the online environment, computer-mediated communication makes it easier to form meaningful relationships among students in the online environment, and computer-mediated communication allows you to feel the presence of their instructor and other students in the online environment.

Table 13. Relationship between Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of Instructor Characteristics, The Feel of a Learning Community and Computer-Mediated Communication and the Use of Gadgets in Learning.

STATEMENTS	Android		Tablet		Laptop		TV/ Radio		Desktop	
	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.
<u>Instructor Characteristics</u>										
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I still get the same explanation from online instructors as I do from traditional instructors.	0.04 ^{ns}	0.69	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.94	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.42	0.19 ⁺	0.03	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.57
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online instructors and traditional instructors offer the same amount of help with my learning issues.	0.07 ^{ns}	0.44	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.67	-0.14 ^{ns}	0.12	0.19 ⁺	0.03	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.43
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because technology makes online instructors more creative in teaching than a more traditional classroom.	0.08 ^{ns}	0.35	-0.18 ^s	0.04	0.08 ^{ns}	0.40	0.18 ⁺	0.04	0.00 ^{ns}	1.00
<u>The Feel of a Learning Community</u>										
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is like a community where I can communicate with other students.	-0.10 ^{ns}	0.91	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.90	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.76	0.20 ⁺	0.03	0.03 ^{ns}	0.72
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment promotes sufficient sharing and caring among students.	0.09 ^{ns}	0.32	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.88	-0.14 ^{ns}	0.12	0.20 ⁺	0.02	0.08 ^{ns}	0.38
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is a safe place where I can be confident in completing group work with other students in the class.	0.11 ^{ns}	0.21	-0.14 ^{ns}	0.11	-0.22 ^{ns}	0.10	0.19 ⁺	0.03	0.04 ^{ns}	0.62
<u>Computer-Mediated Communication</u>										
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes me feel like a real person when I communicate in the online environment.	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.87	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.67	-0.08 ^{ns}	0.36	0.20 ⁺	0.02	-0.06 ^{ns}	0.49
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes it easier to form meaningful relationships among students in the online environment.	-0.12 ^{ns}	0.16	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.91	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.80	0.20 ⁺	0.02	0.00 ^{ns}	1.00
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication allows me to feel the presence of my instructor and other students in the online environment.	0.01 ^{ns}	0.88	0.01 ^{ns}	0.88	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.54	0.21 ⁺	0.02	-0.06 ^{ns}	0.56

Relationship between Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of Use of Internet Connection in Learning

Table 14 shows the relationship between respondents' level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of effectiveness of feedback, timeliness of feedback and use of discussion boards and the use of internet connection in learning.

Effectiveness of Feedback. As reflected on the table, correlation values from 0.07 to -0.03 and significance level from 0.95 to 0.12, respectively indicated no significant relationship. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the use of android, tablet, laptop and desktop in online learning mathematics with the statements "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of clarification for my questions about the course (e.g. assignments)", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of instruction on how to fix incorrect problems in assignments", and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of sufficient explanations on my specific questions related to my class work".

This implied that the use of PLDT, Globe WIFI, Data/Load or Smart Broadband had no bearing on the effective feedback related to their class work which is constantly provided to them in terms of clarification for their questions about the course (e.g. assignments), instruction on how to fix incorrect problems in assignments and sufficient explanations on my specific questions related to their class work.

Timeliness of Feedback. As observed on the table, the correlation values from 0.10 to -0.04 and significance level from 0.97 to 0.09 indicated no significant relationship. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the use of android, tablet, laptop and desktop in online learning mathematics with statements "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to complete my assignments efficiently", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to improve my assignments for better grades", and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am more focused on learning". This implied that the use of PLDT, Globe WIFI, Data/Load or Smart Broadband had no bearing on their satisfaction of online learning in mathematics for timeliness of feedback on their assignments, improve their assignments for better grades and become more focused on learning.

Use of Discussion Boards. As reflected in the table, the correlation values from 0.10 to -0.04 and significance level from 0.97 to 0.09 indicated no significant relationship. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no

significant relationship with the use of PLDT, Globe Wifi, Data/Load and smart broadband in online learning mathematics in terms of use of discussion boards with statements “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because discussion boards make me more comfortable in participating than traditional modes of discussion”, “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because asynchronous discussions (where I can post my discussions at any time of the day) are more convenient to my schedule than traditional discussions”, and “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I have plenty of time to think and draft my responses for online discussions”...

This implied that the use of PLDT, Globe WIFI, Data/Load or Smart Broadband had no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of the use of discussion boards.

Table 14. Relationship between Respondents' Level of Satisfaction on Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of Effective Feedback, Timeliness of the Feedback and Use of Discussion and the Use of Internet Connection in Learning.

STATEMENTS	PLDT		Globe WIFI		Data/Load		Smart Broadband	Sig.
	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	
<u>Effectiveness of Feedback</u>								
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of clarification for my questions about the course (e.g. assignments).	0.04 ^{ns}	0.69	-0.10 ^{ns}	0.24	0.11 ^{ns}	0.22	0.10 ^{ns}	0.27
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of instruction on how to fix incorrect problems in assignments.	0.01 ^{ns}	0.91	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.78	0.08 ^{ns}	0.34	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.93
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of sufficient explanations on my specific questions related to my class work.	0.06 ^{ns}	0.47	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.81	0.02 ^{ns}	0.86	0.10 ^{ns}	0.24
<u>Timeliness of the Feedback</u>								
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to complete my assignments efficiently.	-0.10 ^{ns}	0.28	0.11 ^{ns}	0.20	0.07 ^{ns}	0.42	0.11 ^{ns}	0.22
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to improve my assignments for better grades.	-0.11 ^{ns}	0.19	0.14 ^{ns}	0.12	0.09 ^{ns}	0.29	0.10 ^{ns}	0.26
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am more focused on learning.	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.91	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.65	0.09 ^{ns}	0.33	0.11 ^{ns}	0.23
<u>Use of Discussion Boards</u>								
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because discussion boards make me more comfortable in participating than traditional modes of discussion.	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.68	0.01 ^{ns}	0.89	0.05 ^{ns}	0.61	0.10 ^{ns}	0.24
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because asynchronous discussions (where I can post my discussions at any time of the day) are more convenient to my schedule than traditional discussions.	0.03 ^{ns}	0.70	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.70	0.03 ^{ns}	0.74	0.10 ^{ns}	0.26
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I have plenty of time to think and draft my responses for online discussions.	0.07 ^{ns}	0.85	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.89	0.01 ^{ns}	0.87	0.18 ^s	0.04

Table 15 shows the relationship between respondents' level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of dialogue between instructors and students, perceptions of online experiences, and instructor characteristics and the use of internet connection in learning.

Dialogue between Instructors and Students. The table shows correlation values from 0.07 to -0.05 and significance levels between 0.95 and 0.35, indicating no significant relationship. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted, suggesting that the choice of internet provider (PLDT, Globe WiFi, Data/Load, or Smart Broadband) does not affect students' satisfaction with online mathematics learning, particularly in instructor-student dialogue. This implies that factors beyond internet connectivity, such as teaching strategies, course design, and student engagement, may play a more crucial role in fostering effective communication and interaction in online learning environments.

Perceptions on Online Experiences. As reflected on the table, the correlation values from 0.08 to -0.03 and significance level from 0.79 to 0.39 which shows no significant relationship between the instructor characteristics and internet connection used in learning. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the use of PLDT, Globe Wifi, Data/Load and smart broadband in online learning mathematics in terms of perceptions on online experiences with statements "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because my personal needs as a student are met in the online environment", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because many aspects (features) of online education are enjoyable to me as a learner" and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because overall, I This implied that the use of PLDT, Globe WIFI, Data/Load or Smart Broadband has no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of the perceptions on online experiences.

Instructor Characteristics. The table displays that the correlation values from 0.11 to -0.06 and significance level from 0.83 to 0.10, indicated no significant relationship. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the use of PLDT, Globe Wifi, Data/Load and smart broadband in online learning mathematics in terms of instructor characteristics with statements "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I still get the same explanation from online instructors as I do from traditional instructors", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online instructors and traditional instructors offer the same amount of help with my learning issues" and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because technology makes online instructors more creative in teaching than a more traditional classroom.

Table 15. Relationship between Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of Dialogue between Instructors and Students, Perceptions of On-line Experiences and Instructor Characteristics and the Use of Internet Connection in Learning.

STATEMENTS	PLDT		Globe WIFI		Data/Load		Smart Broadband	
	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.
<u>Dialogue between Instructors and Students</u>								
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I am able to communicate effectively with my instructor throughout the semester.	0.03 ^{ns}	0.77	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.59	0.09 ^{ns}	0.32	-0.09 ^{ns}	0.28
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online dialogue with my instructor helps me as I learn in the online course.	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.45	0.11 ^{ns}	0.20	0.06 ^{ns}	0.48	0.01 ^{ns}	0.92
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I feel less distant in my online learning due to online dialogue with my instructor.	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.41	0.08 ^{ns}	0.36	0.08 ^{ns}	0.35	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.39
<u>Perceptions of Online Experiences</u>								
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because my personal needs as a student are met in the online environment.	0.07 ^{ns}	0.40	-0.12 ^{ns}	0.16	0.08 ^{ns}	0.37	0.01 ^{ns}	0.87
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because many aspects (features) of online education are enjoyable to me as a learner.	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.85	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.82	0.04 ^{ns}	0.64	0.00 ^{ns}	0.96
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because overall, I would rather take online courses than traditional courses.	0.05 ^{ns}	0.58	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.92	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.55	-0.08 ^{ns}	0.36
<u>Instructor Characteristics</u>								
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I still get the same explanation from online instructors as I do from traditional instructors.	0.02 ^{ns}	0.84	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.62	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.88	-0.10 ^{ns}	0.26
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online instructors and traditional instructors offer the same amount of help with my learning issues.	0.10 ^{ns}	0.24	-0.11 ^{ns}	0.21	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.67	-0.09 ^{ns}	0.30
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because technology makes online instructors more creative in teaching than a more traditional classroom.	0.07 ^{ns}	0.42	-0.17 ^s	0.05	0.08 ^{ns}	0.37	-0.09 ^{ns}	0.31

Table 16 shows the relationship between respondents' level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of the feel of a learning community and computer-mediated communication and the use of internet connection in learning.

Feel of a Learning Community. As reflected on the table, the correlation values from 0.11 to -0.03 and significance level from 0.85 to 0.12 show no significant relationship between satisfaction of online learning in terms of feel of a learning community and the internet connection used in learning. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the use of PLDT, Globe Wifi, Data/Load and smart broadband in online learning mathematics in terms of the feel of a learning community with statements "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is like a community where I can communicate with other students", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment promotes sufficient sharing and caring among students", and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is a safe place where I can be confident in completing group work with other students in the class". This implied that the use of PLDT, Globe WIFI, Data/Load or Smart Broadband has no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of the feel of a learning community.

Computer-mediated Communication. As displayed on the table, the correlation values from 0.007 to -0.05 and significance level from 0.095 to 0.10, respectively indicated no significant relationship. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the use of PLDT, Globe Wifi, Data/Load and smart broadband in online learning mathematics in terms of computer-mediated communication for the statements "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes me feel like a real person when I communicate in the online environment", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes it easier to form meaningful relationships among students in the online environment", and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication allows me to feel the presence of my instructor and other students in the online environment". This implied that the use of PLDT, Globe WIFI, Data/Load or Smart Broadband has no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of computer-mediated communication.

Table 16. Relationship between Respondents' Level of Satisfaction on Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of the Feel of a Learning Community and Computer-Mediated Communication and the Use of Internet Connection in Learning.

STATEMENTS	PLDT		Globe WIFI		Data/Load		Smart Broadband	
	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.
<u>The Feel of a Learning Community</u>								
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is like a community where I can communicate with other students.	0.11 ^{ns}	0.22	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.56	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.56	-0.20 ^s	0.02
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment promotes sufficient sharing and caring among students.	0.02 ^{ns}	0.80	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.40	0.03 ^{ns}	0.70	-0.08 ^{ns}	0.36
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is a safe place where I can be confident in completing group work with other students in the class.	0.04 ^{ns}	0.63	-0.12 ^{ns}	0.18	0.06 ^{ns}	0.48	-0.09 ^{ns}	0.29
<u>Computer-Mediated Communication</u>								
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes me feel like a real person when I communicate in the online environment.	0.03 ^{ns}	0.73	0.01 ^{ns}	0.95	0.03 ^{ns}	0.75	-0.17 ^{ns}	0.06
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes it easier to form meaningful relationships among students in the online environment.	0.02 ^{ns}	0.85	0.02 ^{ns}	0.79	0.02 ^{ns}	0.84	0.02 ^{ns}	0.82
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication allows me to feel the presence of my instructor and other students in the online environment.	-0.12 ^{ns}	0.17	0.07 ^{ns}	0.45	0.11 ^{ns}	0.20	0.03 ^{ns}	0.74

^{ns}Not Significant

Relationship between Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in terms of the Usage of Internet per Week in Learning

Table 17 shows the relationship between respondents' level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of effective feedback, timeliness of the feedback and use of discussion boards and dialogue between instructors and students and the usage of internet per week in learning.

Effectiveness of Feedback. As reflected in the table, the correlation values from 0.15 to -0.05 and significance level from 0.57 to 1.00, respectively indicated insignificant relationship. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the usage of internet per week in online learning mathematics in terms of effectiveness of feedback with statements "students were satisfied with their online learning experience because effective feedback related to their class work was constantly provided to them in terms of clarification for their questions about the course (e.g. assignments)", "students were satisfied with their online learning experience because effective feedback related to their class work was constantly provided to them in terms of instruction on how to fix incorrect problems in assignments" and "students were satisfied with their online learning experience because effective feedback related to their class work was constantly provided to them in terms of sufficient explanations on their specific questions related to their class work". This implied that internet usage has no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of the effectiveness of feedback.

Timeliness of Feedback. As presented on the table, the correlation values from 0.12 to 0.03 and significance level from 0.77 to 0.16 reflected an insignificant relationship. This resulted in the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the usage of internet per week in online learning mathematics in terms of timeliness of feedback. This implied that the "they were satisfied with their online learning experience because timely feedback related to their class work is constantly provided to them so that they able to complete their assignments efficiently", "they were satisfied with their online learning experience because timely feedback related to their class work is constantly provided to them so that I am able to improve my assignments for better grades", and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am more focused on learning". This implies that internet usage has no bearing on satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of the timeliness of feedback.

Use of Discussion Boards. As shown on the table, the correlation values from -0.01 to -0.07 and significance level from 0.92 to 0.40 represented the insignificant relationship between use of discussion boards and internet usage. This resulted in the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the usage of internet per week in online learning mathematics in terms of use of discussion boards. This implied that "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because discussion boards make me more comfortable in participating than traditional modes of discussion", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because asynchronous discussions

(where I can post my discussions at any time of the day) are more convenient to my schedule than traditional discussions”, and “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I have plenty of time to think and draft my responses for online discussions”. This implies that the internet usage has no bearing on the satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of the use of discussion boards.

Dialogue between Instructors and Students. As seen on the table, the correlation values from 0.03 to -0.01 and significance level from 0.98 to 0.74, respectively indicated no significant relationship. This resulted in the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the usage of the internet per week in online learning mathematics in terms of dialogue between instructors and students. This implies that internet usage has no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of the dialogue between instructors and students.

Table 17. Relationship between Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Terms of Effective Feedback, Timeliness of the Feedback, Use of Discussion Boards and Dialogue between Instructors and Students and the Usage of Internet per week in Learning.

STATEMENTS	Frequency of use the internet	
	Corr.	Sig.
<u>Effectiveness of Feedback</u>		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of clarification for my questions about the course (e.g. assignments).	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.57
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of sufficient explanations on my specific questions related to my class work.	0.15 ^{ns}	0.07
<u>Timeliness of the Feedback</u>		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to complete my assignments efficiently.	0.03 ^{ns}	0.77
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to improve my assignments for better grades.	0.12 ^{ns}	0.16
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am more focused on learning.	0.05 ^{ns}	0.59
<u>Use of Discussion Boards</u>		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because discussion boards make me more comfortable in participating than traditional modes of discussion.	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.61
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because asynchronous discussions (where I can post my discussions at any time of the day) are more convenient to my schedule than traditional discussions.	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.40
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I have plenty of time to think and draft my responses for online discussions.	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.92
<u>Dialogue between Instructors and Students</u>		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I am able to communicate effectively with my instructor throughout the semester.	0.03 ^{ns}	0.74
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online dialogue with my instructor helps me as I learn in the online course.	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.91

3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I feel less distant in my online learning due to online dialogue with my instructor. 0.00^{ns} 0.98

^{ns} Not Significant

Table 18 displays the relationship between respondent's level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of perceptions of online experiences, instructor characteristics, the feel of a learning community and computer-mediated communication and the use of internet per week in learning.

Perceptions of Online Experiences. As shown on the table, the correlation values from 0.04 to -0.06 and significance level from 0.74 to 0.47, respectively indicated no significant relationship. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the usage of internet per week in online learning mathematics in terms of perceptions in online learning with the statements "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because my personal needs as a student are met in the online environment", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because many aspects (features) of online education are enjoyable to me as a learner" and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because overall, I would rather take online courses than traditional courses". This implied that internet usage per week had no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of the perceptions of online experiences.

Instructor Characteristics. As displayed on the table, the correlation values from 0.02 to -0.05 and significance level from 0.84 to 0.56, respectively indicated no significant relationship. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the usage of internet per week in online learning mathematics in terms of perceptions in online experiences with the statements "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I still get the same explanation from online instructors as I do from traditional instructors", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online instructors and traditional instructors offer the same amount of help with my learning issues", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because technology makes online instructors more creative in teaching than a more traditional classroom". This implied that the internet usage per week had no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of the instructor characteristics and the internet usage per week in learning.

The Feel of a Learning Community. As reflected on the table, the correlation values from 0.01 to -0.06 and significance level from 0.88 to 0.47, respectively indicated no significant relationship. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the usage of internet per week in online learning mathematics in terms of the feel of a learning community with the statements "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is like a community where I can communicate with other students", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment promotes sufficient sharing and caring among students", and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is a safe place where I can be confident in completing group work with other students in the class". This implied that the internet usage per week had no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of the feel of a learning community.

Computer-mediated Communication. As gleaned on the table, the correlation values from 0.29 to -0.01 and significance level from 0.76 to 0.49 respectively indicated insignificant relationship. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the usage of internet per week in online learning mathematics in terms of computer-mediated communication with the statements “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes me feel like a real person when I communicate in the online environment”, “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes it easier to form meaningful relationships among students in the online environment”, and “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication allows me to feel the presence of my instructor and other students in the online environment”. This implied that the internet usage per week had no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics have no relationship in terms of the computer-mediated communication.

Table 18. Relationship between Respondents’ Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of Perceptions of On-line Experiences, Instructor Characteristics, the Feel of a Learning Community and Computer-mediated Communication and the Use of Internet Per Week in Learning.

STATEMENTS	Frequency of use the internet	
	Corr.	Sig.
<u>Perceptions of Online Experiences</u>		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because my personal needs as a student are met in the online environment.	-0.06 ^{ns}	0.47
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because many aspects (features) of online education are enjoyable to me as a learner.	0.03 ^{ns}	0.74
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because overall, I would rather take online courses than traditional courses.	0.04 ^{ns}	0.65
<u>Instructor Characteristics</u>		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I still get the same explanation from online instructors as I do from traditional instructors.	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.56
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online instructors and traditional instructors offer the same amount of help with my learning issues.	0.02 ^{ns}	0.82
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because technology makes online instructors more creative in teaching than a more traditional classroom.	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.84
<u>The feel of a Learning Community</u>		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is like a community where I can communicate with other students.	0.01 ^{ns}	0.88

2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment promotes sufficient sharing and caring among students	-0.06 ^{ns}	0.47
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is a safe place where I can be confident in completing group work with other students in the class.	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.70

Computer-Mediated Communication

1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes me feel like a real person when I communicate in the online environment.	0.29 ^{ns}	0.73
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes it easier to form meaningful relationships among students in the online environment	0.06 ^{ns}	0.49
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication allows me to feel the presence of my instructor and other students in the online environment.	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.76

^{ns} Not Significant

Relationship between Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in terms of the Academic Performance in Mathematics

Table 19 displays the relationship between respondent's level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of effectiveness of feedback, timeliness of feedback, use of discussion boards, dialogue between instructor and students and perceptions of online experiences and the academic performance in mathematics.

Effectiveness of Feedback. As seen on the table, correlation values from 0.06 to -0.03 and significance levels from 0.70 to 0.40 respectively indicated insignificant relationship between the satisfaction of online learning in mathematics and the academic performance in mathematics. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the academic performance in online learning mathematics in terms of effectiveness of feedback with the statements "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of clarification for my questions about the course (e.g. assignments)", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of instruction on how to fix incorrect problems in assignments", and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of sufficient explanations on my specific questions related to my class work". This implied that the respondent's academic performance in mathematics had no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of the effectiveness of feedback.

Timeliness of Feedback. As presented on the table, the correlation values from 0.03 to -0.02 and significance levels from 0.91 to 0.71, respectively indicated no

significant relationship between the satisfaction of online leaning in mathematics and the academic performance in mathematics. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the academic performance in online learning mathematics in terms of timeliness of feedback with the statements “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to complete my assignments efficiently”, “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to improve my assignments for better grades”, and “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am more focused on learning”. This implied that the respondent’s academic performance in mathematics had no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics have not connected in terms of the timeliness of feedback.

“At the time of providing feedback it is important that after reading that a student should have a positive feeling about that feedback. This is considered as a process of motivating the students to utilize the feedback they have received. Feedback should not be discouraging the students at any cost.

Use of Discussion Boards. As reflected on the table, the correlation values from -0.04 to -0.07 and significance levels from 0.57 to 0.39, respectively indicated no significant relationship between the satisfaction of online leaning in mathematics and the academic performance in mathematics. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the academic performance in online learning mathematics in terms of timeliness of feedback with the statements “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because discussion boards make me more comfortable in participating than traditional modes of discussion”, “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because asynchronous discussions (where I can post my discussions at any time of the day) are more convenient to my schedule than traditional discussions”, and “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I have plenty of time to think and draft my responses for online discussions”. This implied that the respondent’s academic performance in mathematics had no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of the use of discussion boards.

Dialogue between Instructors and Students. As observed on the table, the correlation values from 0.06 to -0.04 and significance level from 0.95 to 0.43, respectively indicated no significant relationship between the satisfaction of online leaning in mathematics and the academic performance in mathematics. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the academic performance in online learning mathematics in terms of dialogue between instructors and students with the statements “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I am able to communicate effectively with my instructor throughout the semester”, “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online dialogue with my instructor helps me as I learn in the online course”, and “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I feel less distant in my online learning due to online dialogue with my instructor”. This implied that the respondent’s

academic performance in mathematics had no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics have no significant relationship in terms of the dialogue between instructors and students.

Perceptions of Online Experiences. As observed on the table, the correlation values from -0.03 to -0.04 and significance level from 0.73 to 0.57, respectively indicated insignificant relationship between the satisfaction of online leaning in mathematics and the academic performance in mathematics. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the academic performance in online learning mathematics in terms of perceptions in online learning with the statements “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because my personal needs as a student are met in the online environment”, “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because many aspects (features) of online education are enjoyable to me as a learner” and “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because overall, I would rather take online courses than traditional courses”. This implied that the respondent’s academic performance in mathematics had no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics have no significant relationship in terms of the perceptions in online experiences.

Table 19. Relationship between Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of Effective Feedback, Timeliness of the Feedback, Use of Discussion Boards, Dialogue between Instructors and Students and Perceptions of On-line Experiences and the Academic Performance in Mathematics.

STATEMENTS	Academic Performance	
	Corr.	Sig.
<u>Effectiveness of Feedback</u>		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of clarification for my questions about the course (e.g. assignments).	0.03 ^{ns}	0.70
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of instruction on how to fix incorrect problems in assignments.	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.70
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because effective feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me in terms of sufficient explanations on my specific questions related to my class work.	0.06 ^{ns}	0.40
<u>Timeliness of the Feedback</u>		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to complete my assignments efficiently.	0.03 ^{ns}	0.71
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am able to improve my assignments for better grades.	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.91
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because timely feedback related to my class work is constantly provided to me so that I am more focused on learning.	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.82
<u>Use of Discussion Boards</u>		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because discussion boards make me more comfortable in participating than traditional modes of discussion.	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.57

2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because asynchronous discussions (where I can post my discussions at any time of the day) are more convenient to my schedule than traditional discussions	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.39
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I have plenty of time to think and draft my responses for online discussions	-0.06 ^{ns}	0.43
<u>Dialogue between Instructors and Students</u>		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I am able to communicate effectively with my instructor throughout the semester	0.06 ^{ns}	0.43
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online dialogue with my instructor helps me as I learn in the online course	0.00 ^{ns}	0.95
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I feel less distant in my online learning due to online dialogue with my instructor	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.59
<u>Perceptions of Online Experiences</u>		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because my personal needs as a student are met in the online environment	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.66
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because many aspects (features) of online education are enjoyable to me as a learner	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.57
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because overall, I would rather take online courses than traditional courses	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.73

Table 21 displays the relationship between respondent's level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics in terms of instructor characteristics, the feel of a learning community and computer-mediated communication and the academic performance in mathematics.

Instructor Characteristics As shown on the table, the correlation values from -0.01 to -0.07 and significance levels from 0.89 to 0.33, respectively indicated insignificant relationship between the satisfaction of online learning in mathematics and the academic performance in mathematics. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the academic performance in online learning mathematics in terms of instructor characteristics with the statements "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I still get the same explanation from online instructors as I do from traditional instructors", "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online instructors and traditional instructors offer the same amount of help with my learning issues" and "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because technology makes online instructors more creative in teaching than a more traditional classroom". This implied that the respondent's academic performance in mathematics had no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics have no significant relationship in terms of the instructor characteristics.

The Feel of a Learning Community. As reflected on the table, the correlation values from -0.05 to -0.10 and significance levels from 0.52 to 0.20, respectively indicated no significant relationship between the satisfaction of online learning in mathematics and the academic performance in mathematics. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the academic performance in online learning mathematics in terms of the feel of a learning community with the statements "I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is like a community where I can communicate with other students", "I am

satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment promotes sufficient sharing and caring among students”, and “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is a safe place where I can be confident in completing group work with other students in the class”. This implied that the respondent’s academic performance in mathematics had no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics have no significant relationship in terms of the feel of a learning community.

Computer-mediated Communication. As presented on the table, the correlation values from 0.00 to -0.05 and significance level from 0.96 to 0.48, respectively indicated no significant relationship between the satisfaction of online learning in mathematics and the academic performance in mathematics. This resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship with the academic performance in online learning mathematics in terms of computer-mediated communication with the statements “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes me feel like a real person when I communicate in the online environment”, “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes it easier to form meaningful relationships among students in the online environment”, and “I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication allows me to feel the presence of my instructor and other students in the online environment”. This implied that the respondents academic performance in mathematics had no bearing on the level of satisfaction of online learning in mathematics have no significant relationship in terms of the computer-mediated communication and the academic performance in mathematics.

Table 21. Relationship between Respondents' Level of Satisfaction of Online Learning in Mathematics in Terms of Instructor Characteristics, the Feel of a Learning Community and Computer-Mediated Communication and the Academic Performance in Mathematics.

STATEMENTS	Academic Performance	
	Corr.	Sig.
<u>Instructor Characteristics</u>		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because I still get the same explanation from online instructors as I do from traditional instructors.	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.75
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because online instructors and traditional instructors offer the same amount of help with my learning issues.	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.89
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because technology makes online instructors more creative in teaching than a more traditional classroom.	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.33
<u>The Feel of a Learning Community</u>		
1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is like a community where I can communicate with other students.	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.52
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment promotes sufficient sharing and caring among students.	-0.06 ^{ns}	0.44

3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because the online environment is a safe place where I can be confident in completing group work with other students in the class. -0.10^{ns} 0.20

Computer-Mediated Communication

1. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes me feel like a real person when I communicate in the online environment. -0.05^{ns} 0.53
2. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication makes it easier to form meaningful relationships among students in the online environment. -0.05^{ns} 0.48
3. I am satisfied with my online learning experience because computer-mediated communication allows me to feel the presence of my instructor and other students in the online environment. 0.00^{ns} 0.96

^{ns}Not Significant

DISCUSSION

This study was conducted to determine the relationship and difference of the students' level of satisfaction and academic performance in mathematics of Junior High School students as to their profile.

The respondents of this study comprised of 121 Junior High School students of Jet Montessori School of Ramon, Inc. for the school year 2021-2022.

A descriptive correlational design was used in the study. This study also employed inferential statistics to test the hypotheses of the study.

The hypotheses of the study were: "There is no significant difference between the students' level of satisfaction in online learning in mathematics and the profile of the respondents" and "There is no significant relationship between the students' level of satisfaction in online learning in mathematics and the profile of the respondents."

The main instrument of the study was a questionnaire that had two parts. Part I of the questionnaire focused on the personal profile (Age, Gender, Technology use in terms of gadgets, internet connection and internet usage, and Academic performance in Mathematics) while Part II focused on the students' level of satisfaction in online learning mathematics of the learners. The questionnaire was based on the attitude survey from Satisfaction of Online Learning (SOL). This included 24 items embedded in eight components that were developed, 3 items each statements for all the students' level of satisfaction. .

The data gathered were computer-processed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

From the data gathered, the findings are summarized as follows:

Majority of the respondents were 15 years old. Most of them were female. With regards to the gadgets used, majority of the respondents had an android phone. On their

internet connection, most of them were using PLDT Home Fiber and in the frequency of use, majority of them used the internet every day.

On the students' level of satisfaction in learning mathematics, the results revealed that the respondents had described all the statements as "agree" for effectiveness of feedback, timeliness of feedback, use of discussion boards, dialogue between instructors and students, perception in online learning, instructor characteristics, feeling of a learning community and computer-mediated communication.

In connection with the difference in the respondents' level of satisfaction in mathematics according to their profile, the results revealed that there was no significant difference on their level of satisfaction when grouped according to age, gender, academic performance in mathematics and technology used in terms of gadgets use, internet connection and frequency use of internet.

For the relationship between the respondents' level of satisfaction in learning mathematics and age, there was no significant relationship between their level of satisfaction and their age.

It also exposed the relationship between the respondents' level of satisfaction in mathematics and the internet connection used in learning that there was no significant relationship between their level of satisfaction and the use of internet connection.

It was revealed on the relationship between the respondents' level of satisfaction in mathematics and the internet usage in learning that there was no significant relationship between level of satisfactions and the internet usage. On the relationship between the respondents' level of satisfaction in learning mathematics and academic performance, the results revealed that there was no significant relationship between the level of satisfaction and their academic performance.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were made:

For the students' level of satisfaction in mathematics, the respondents were satisfied on the learning of mathematics online.

With regards to the difference of their level of satisfaction and profile, there was no significant difference on their level of satisfaction when grouped according to age, gender, technology used in terms of gadgets used, internet connection and frequency in usage and academic performance in mathematics.

As to the relationship between the respondents' level of satisfaction in learning mathematics and the use of gadgets, there was a significant relationship between their instructor characteristics, the feel of a learning community and the computer-mediated communication and the use of android, desktop, laptop and tablet while there was a significant relationship between instructor characteristics, the feel of a learning community

and the computer-mediated communication and the use of TV/Radio in terms of gadgets used in learning mathematics.

With the relationship between the respondents' level of satisfaction in mathematics and the internet connection used in learning, there was no significant

And finally, the relationship between the respondents' level of satisfaction in mathematics and academic performance showed that there was no significant relationship between the students' level of satisfaction and the use of internet connection.

The relationship between the respondents' level of satisfaction and the internet usage in learning showed that there was no significant relationship between the level of satisfaction and the usage of internet connection.

Recommendations

Based on the result of this study, the researcher recommends the following:

For the students, they should encourage themselves in online learning in mathematics to boost their confidence and have a better performance in mathematics.

For the teachers, they are suggested to attend seminars through online learning platforms that will help them innovate ideas for effective online teaching of mathematics.

For the parents, they are encouraged to provide enough internet connections that would encourage their children to attend in the online learning in mathematics. They must assist their children through the online class.

For the school administrators, they are suggested to organize a program that covers the satisfaction of the students in online learning of mathematics.

Lastly, for the future researchers, they are encouraged to conduct another study related to the level of satisfaction in online learning of mathematics covering other factors that are not discussed on this study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers ensured that ethical considerations were strictly followed throughout the study. From data collection, informed consent was obtained from all respondents, and they were fully informed about the purpose, nature, and objectives of the research. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and respondents were given the freedom to withdraw at any stage without any consequences. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained, ensuring that no personally identifiable information was disclosed. The well-being of the respondents was safeguarded, and the research did not pose any psychological, emotional, or physical harm to them. Additionally, the study was conducted with integrity, avoiding any form of plagiarism, and ensuring that all sources were properly cited. There was no bias in the interpretation of

findings and all results were presented objectively and accurately.

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